

Information for data subjects according to the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (EU GDPR) of the MIRRI-ERIC Privacy Policy

MIRRI-ERIC operates under the data protection framework - known as [Privacy Policy](#) which is adapted to the needs of international scientific research and reflects the principles of European data protection law.

1. **Personal data provided by you that we process:** Personal details: name, last name, institutional email address, institution affiliation, country (of employer institution).
2. **Purpose(s) of processing:**
 - a) Create mailing lists for the management of MIRRI-ERIC activities;
 - b) Provide access to the MIRRI-ERIC repositories;
 - c) Communications regarding reporting requirements of MIRRI-ERIC coordinated activities.
3. **How we will use the data:** email addresses will be used to create activities lists and allow access to the MIRRI-ERIC repositories. Email addresses will also be used to get in touch with you in relation to MIRRI-ERIC activities.
4. **Legal basis:** the processing of your personal data is necessary for the MIRRI-ERIC day- to-day management, operation and functioning.
5. **Who has access to the data:** MIRRI-ERIC CCU and individuals involved in the management of its activities.
6. **External data processors:** MIRRI-ERIC engages the services of Google Ltd and Synology to achieve the purposes outlined above. Google Ltd is a global operator who is subject to GDPR as well as other data protection laws applicable to it. Google Ltd may transfer your personal data outside the EU/EEA area, including the United States.

- 7. Data retention:** your data will be stored in MIRRI-ERIC's repositories for as long as necessary for the achievement of the purpose(s) you have enrolled. Data will be retained during that period and deleted once it has ended as soon as the retention period established by the European Commission is over.
- 8. Your rights:** Any person may exercise the following rights over the files owned by MIRRI- ERIC, in the terms established by the EU GDPR:
- Right of access to your personal data and to know which ones are being processed and the processing operations carried out with them.
 - Right to correct any inaccurate data. - Right to delete your personal data.
 - Right to object or limit to the processing of your personal data.
 - Right to data portability.
 - Right to revoke your consent at any time.
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